

A Study of Tragic Elements through Euripides' *Electra*

Ms. Patil Vibhali Ashok¹ & Dr. Abhijeet Nanasaheb Pawar²

¹M.A.-II Student, Department of English,

Sadguru Gadge Maharaj College, Karad, Satara (M.S.) India

²Assistant Professor, Department of English,

Sadguru Gadge Maharaj College, Karad, Satara (M.S.) India

Corresponding Author – Ms. Patil Vibhali Ashok

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Abstract:

This research paper aims to examine the tragic elements in *Electra* by Euripides through the lens of Aristotelian theory of tragedy. Aristotle in his work *Poetics* defines tragedy as an imitation of serious action that arouses pity and fear, leading to catharsis. *Electra* presents a powerful story of revenge, justice, and moral conflict. This study explores how Euripides presents tragic elements such as hamartia (tragic flaw), revenge, suffering, and psychological realism. By analyzing characters like *Electra* and *Orestes*, the paper shows how the play creates pity and fear in the audience. It also examines how Euripides departs from traditional heroic tragedy by presenting more human and realistic characters. The study concludes that *Electra* is not just a story of revenge but also a deep exploration of human emotions and moral dilemmas.

Keywords: *Tragedy, Aristotle, Euripides, Electra, Revenge, Catharsis, Hamartia.*

The foundation of Western dramatic theory begins with Aristotle's *Poetics*. According to Aristotle, tragedy is the imitation of a serious and complete action that produces feelings of pity and fear, leading to catharsis. Euripides, one of the great Greek tragedians, presents a unique approach to tragedy in *Electra*. Unlike traditional Greek tragedies that focus on heroic characters, Euripides presents ordinary and emotionally complex individuals.

The story of *Electra* is based on the myth of the House of Atreus. *Electra* and her brother *Orestes* seek revenge for the murder of their father *Agamemnon* by their mother *Clytemnestra* and her lover *Aegisthus*. This theme of revenge forms the central tragic element of the play. However, Euripides does not present revenge as heroic; instead, he shows its painful and disturbing consequences.

One of the important elements of Aristotelian tragedy is Hamartia or tragic flaw. In *Electra*, the tragic flaw is not just in one character but shared by both *Electra* and *Orestes*. *Electra*'s excessive desire for revenge and her inability to forgive become her weakness. Similarly, *Orestes* is torn between his duty to avenge his father and his moral hesitation about killing his own mother. This internal conflict creates deep emotional tension in the play.

Another important tragic element is pathos or suffering. *Electra* is shown living in poverty and humiliation, married to a poor farmer to prevent her from having noble children. Her suffering creates sympathy in the audience. According to Aristotle, tragedy should evoke pity and fear. In *Electra*, the audience feels pity for *Electra*'s condition and fear when she and *Orestes* plan the murder of *Clytemnestra*.

Euripides also uses recognition (Anagnorisis) in the play. The moment when Electra recognizes Orestes is different from other versions of the myth. Instead of using dramatic and heroic signs, Euripides presents a more realistic and simple recognition scene. This shows his focus on realism rather than tradition.

The peripeteia (reversal of fortune) is seen when the plan of revenge is successfully carried out. However, instead of bringing happiness, it leads to guilt and emotional suffering. After killing their mother, both Electra and Orestes feel disturbed and regretful. This is where Euripides differs from traditional tragedy. He shows that revenge does not bring peace but creates more pain.

Another important aspect of Euripides' tragedy is psychological realism. Characters are not shown as ideal heroes but as real human beings with emotions and doubts. Electra is not just a revenge-seeking daughter; she is also a woman filled with pain, anger, and confusion. Orestes is not a strong hero but a man struggling with moral guilt. The role of the chorus in *Electra* also contributes to the tragic effect. The chorus represents the voice of society and comments on the actions of the characters. It expresses sympathy for Electra and also questions the morality of revenge. This helps the audience to reflect on the ethical issues in the play.

Unlike other tragedians like Sophocles and Aeschylus, Euripides presents a more critical view of traditional values. He challenges the idea that revenge is justified. By showing the emotional consequences of violence, he creates a

more modern and realistic form of tragedy. Thus, *Electra* follows many elements of Aristotelian tragedy such as plot, pity, fear, and catharsis. However, Euripides also modifies these elements by focusing on human psychology and moral complexity.

From the above analysis, it is clear that *Electra* by Euripides is a powerful example of Greek tragedy that both follows and challenges Aristotelian principles. The play successfully creates pity and fear through the suffering of its characters and leads to catharsis.

However, Euripides goes beyond traditional tragedy by presenting realistic and psychologically complex characters. He shows that revenge is not a simple act of justice but a source of pain and guilt. Through *Electra* and *Orestes*, he explores the darker side of human emotions. Therefore, *Electra* is not only a story of revenge but also a deep study of human nature, morality, and suffering. It remains relevant even today because it raises important questions about justice and ethics.

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